

Contents

PAPERS

- | | | | |
|--|--|--|---|
| <p>Polycentric forest governance for social equity of Indigenous Peoples? A critical appraisal
D. ADHIKARI</p> <p>The transformation of institutional capacity for social forestry policy in Java, Indonesia
M. ADIB, M. SAUD, R. RUSTINSYAH and I. ABDULLAH</p> <p>A comparative legal analysis of silvicultural interventions for sustainable forest management
Ü. BİRBEN and F. ÇAKIR</p> <p>An assessment of export-import performances of Nepal's wood sector: market landscape and trade indices analysis
R.B. DANGI</p> <p>Energy forests on small rural properties in the semi-arid region of Brazil
D.C. GAMA, D.A. DEUS, T.A.S. FREITAS, F.F. OLIVEIRA, M.D.S. FONSECA and A.C.P. SANTOS</p> | <p>1</p> <p>16</p> <p>29</p> <p>42</p> <p>55</p> | <p>Unlocking the potential of private forests for carbon storage, biodiversity conservation, and livelihoods in Nepal
R. JOSHI, H. ZHANG, T. MARASENI, N. DHAKAL, J. GAUTAM, H. SINGH and H. ADHIKARI</p> <p>Youth knowledge, engagement, and challenges in forest management and governance in Africa: a literature review
C. WEKESA, A. ROOS, D. GITONGA, L. POPOOLA, D. MUTTA, M-L. AVANA-TIENTCHEU, C. MARK-HERBERT, F. BABALOLA, J. CHEBOIWO and P. MBILE</p> <p>Empirical analysis of the links between China's forest product imports and tropical forest loss
X. SUN, A.L. HAMMETT and R. BUSH</p> <p>BOOK REVIEW
Resilient Forest Management
<i>Philip J. Burton</i></p> | <p>67</p> <p>85</p> <p>102</p> <p>113</p> |
|--|--|--|---|

THE INTERNATIONAL FORESTRY REVIEW

Vol. 28 (1), 2026

The International Forestry Review

EDITOR: A.J. POTTINGER

International Forestry Review (print) ISSN 1465-5489
International Forestry Review (online) ISSN 2053-7778

PUBLISHED BY THE COMMONWEALTH FORESTRY ASSOCIATION

Vol.28(1), 2026

www.cfa-international.org

The International Forestry Review

Editor

Alan Pottinger
alan.pottinger@cfa-international.org

Editorial Board

Fred Babweteera
Budongo Conservation Field Station, Uganda

Neil Byron
Independent, Australia

José Joaquín Campos
CATIE, Costa Rica

Jim Carle
Independent, New Zealand

Ebby Chagala
Kenya Forestry Research Institute (KEFRI), Nairobi, Kenya

Ben Chikamai
Executive Secretary, Network for Natural Gums and Resins in Africa (NGARA)

Mafa Chipeta
Independent, Malawi

Jonathan Cornelius
World Agroforestry Centre (ICRAF), Peru

Julian Evans
Independent, UK

Lukas Giessen
Technical University Dresden, Germany

Verina Ingram
CIFOR, Indonesia and LEI Wageningen UR, The Netherlands

Contact

The Editor, International Forestry Review,
The Crib, Dinchope, Shropshire SY7 9JJ, UK
Telephone: +44 (0)1588 672868
Email: cfa@cfa-international.org,
Web: www.cfa-international.org

Cover photo: Youth participants explore ideas for home-grown green enterprises during the #AfricanYouth4Forests workshop in Voi, Kenya, 2022, guided by scientific insights from Dr. Doris Mutta of the African Forest Forum (AFF) (*Credit: Felix Odhiambo*).

Chairman of the Editorial Board

Jeff Sayer
University of British Columbia, Canada
jeffrey.sayer@ubc.ca

John Innes
University of British Columbia, Canada

Peter Kanowski
Australian National University, Australia

Roger Leakey
James Cook University, Australia

John Palmer
University of British Columbia, Canada

Gill Petrokofsky
University of Oxford, UK

Jack Putz
University of Florida, USA

Lee Su See
Forestry Research Institute Malaysia, Malaysia

Changyou Sun
Mississippi State University, USA

Terry Sunderland
University of British Columbia, Canada

Jerome Vanclay
Southern Cross University, Australia

Michael J. Wingfield
Forest and Agricultural Biotechnology Institute (FABI), South Africa

GUIDELINES FOR AUTHORS

Please send the Summary of the paper to the Editor at cfa@cfa-international.org. If it is considered suitable for consideration you will be asked to send the complete manuscript. Manuscripts submitted for consideration must conform to the following points. Any deviation will result in the manuscript being returned to the author.

COMPOSITION

- Contributions must be original* and not have been submitted for publication elsewhere. (Note: Plagiarism is evaluated by use of electronic software. For more information on what constitutes plagiarism, and why it is important please click here).
- The text, excluding tables, references and appendices, should not exceed 7000 words, although exceptions may be permitted in special cases.
- A SUMMARY of not more than 150 words must be supplied, together with 5 keywords.
- All spelling must conform to UK/international English.
- The layout of the text and style of table and figure legends and references must conform to that of the International Forestry Review. This means:
 - Main title in Arial, Text in Times New Roman
 - The hierarchy of headings is: CAPITALS, **bold lower case**, *italics lower case*.

TEXT

- Manuscripts should be produced in Microsoft Word, written in Times New Roman typeface (size 12 pt), with single row spacing, left justification and without hyphenation.
- The manuscript should be written in the passive voice, e.g. 'The experiment was carried out' *is correct*; 'We carried out the experiment' *is incorrect*.
- Manuscripts should be submitted with UK English spellings. Make sure that a spell check with UK English spellings is used prior to submission.
- Paragraphs should not be separated by any additional line spacing. The first paragraph in a section should not be indented. The first line of each subsequent paragraph should be indented to 1.27cm.
- Use quotation marks (" ") *only* around quotations or titles. Do not use them to highlight or emphasise text.
- et al.* *is correct*. *et al* *is incorrect*.
- The document should be saved as a Microsoft Word file with *.doc file extension.

TITLE

- The title and author's details should be in the following format

Mutually beneficial company-community partnership in ensuring its long-term viability: emerging lessons from Indonesia

A.A. NAWIR and L. SANTOSO

Center for International Forestry Research, Jl. CIFOR, Situ Gede, Sindang Barang, Bogor 16680, Indonesia

Email: a.nawir@cgjar.org and l.santoso@cgjar.org

TABLES

- Tables should clear and simple, with a maximum of 8 columns. (Note that tables have limited space in the final layout and therefore the reduction of font size to a minimum of 8 pt during typesetting should be taken into account when preparing tables).
- Headings and other texts in table cells should to be concise. Tables including captions, legends and footnotes should be written in Microsoft Word (in exceptional cases Microsoft Excel can be used following agreement of the Editor).
- Tables should be saved in a separate file (not as an integral part of manuscript) and the manuscript text should contain the reference to the position of the table (or figure) in brackets.

NUMBERS

- Numbers greater than 999 should be written with appropriate spaces and without commas, e.g 10 000 is correct, 10,000 and 10000 are incorrect

FOOTNOTES

- References to footnotes in the main text should be marked with arabic numerals in superscript form.

GRAPHS AND FIGURES

- Graphs, diagrams and other figures should be prepared in Microsoft Excel or in Microsoft PowerPoint and saved in separate files. Graphs and diagrams should be drawn in 2-D form (not in 3-D spatial form) and single columns or circle sectors (in case of pie diagrams) should be filled with grayscale colours (not with colour filling or by using of automatic hatching). The line weight of axes and other lines and also the size of used letters or numerals should be appropriate to the final size reduction of diagrams during layout of final magazine page (maximum width of finally reduced diagram is either 8 or 18 cm depending on whether it fits one or two columns).
- Complex images such as maps (drawn in line draw or grayscale format) should be prepared in one of the following: CorelDraw, Adobe Illustrator, Adobe Photoshop, Macromedia Freehand or similar in which he finished images can be saved as *.eps (Encapsulated PostScript) file format. B&W photographs should be submitted as *.tif image file format with a resolution of at least 300 dpi. Colour

photographs may be submitted only after agreement with the Editor. Colour images should be saved in CMYK colour format, as *.tif file format and with a resolution of at least 300 dpi.

- Titles should be in the format: TABLE X *Title of table*

SCIENTIFIC NAMES

- The complete scientific name (genus, species, authority and, where appropriate, cultivar) should be cited at the first occasion of its mention and written in italics (authority in normal type). If vernacular names are used, they must be accompanied by the correct scientific name at first use.

CITATIONS

- For text citations, papers should be referred to as (Smith 1998) and papers by the same author in the same year should be distinguished by lettering in sequence (1998a, 1998b, etc.). Where papers are written by a single author or two authors their names should be cited. If three or more authors are involved the first name should be listed followed by 'et al.', e.g. (Smith *et al.* 2002).
- Citations should be separated by a comma, not a semi-colon, i.e. (Johnstone 2003, Smith 2002, Smith *et al.* 2002).
- Multiple citations by different authors should be listed alphabetically, e.g. (Brown 2001, Jones 2003 and Smith 2002).
- Multiple citations by the same author should conform to the following format (Brown 2001, 2005, 2009).

QUOTATIONS

- Direct quotations from papers or books should be referenced in the format (Smith 1998: 23-24).

REFERENCES

- At the end of the paper, the list of references must be arranged in alphabetical ordering without serial numbering.
- References should be formatted with a 'hanging' indent.
- There should be no additional line spacing between individual references.
- The following standard forms of citation must be used:
 - Author's name, all authors' initials to follow surname, journal and book titles in italics. Volume number in bold. Second and subsequent lines should not be indented. For example:

Journal paper
LÄHDE, E., LAIHO, O., NOROKORPI, Y. and SAKSA, T. 1999. Stand structure as the basis of diversity index. *Forest Ecology and Management* **115** (2/3): 213-220.

Paper or chapter in proceedings
SMITH, W.J. 2001. Selection of tree species for arid environments. In: BLACKBURN, J.W. (ed.) *Multipurpose trees and shrubs for fuelwood and agroforestry*. CNRD Monograph No4. 366 pp.

Book
PHILLIP, M.S. 1994. *Measuring trees and forests*. 2nd edition, CAB International, Wallingford, England. 310 pp.

- Unnecessary use of capitals should be avoided. For example HOLMGREN, J., JOYCE, S., NILSSON, M. and OLSSON. H. 2000. Estimating Stem Volume and Basal Area in Forest Compartments by Combining Satellite Image Data with Field Data. *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research* 15: 103–111. *Is incorrect*.
- HOLMGREN, J., JOYCE, S., NILSSON, M. and OLSSON. H. 2000. Estimating stem volume and basal area in forest compartments by combining satellite image data with field data. *Scandinavian Journal of Forest Research* 15: 103–111. *Is correct*.
- Websites should only be quoted in isolation where hard copies are not available.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

- It is necessary for authors to acknowledge suggestions made by referees with a simple statement such as 'The valuable suggestions made by anonymous referees is gratefully acknowledged'.

SUBMISSION

- Manuscripts offered for publication should be submitted by email to cfa@cfa-international.org

REFEREEING

- Contributions will be referred to at least two expert referees. Authors will be consulted if the paper is considered suitable but alterations are thought desirable. After alterations have been agreed and incorporated, the paper will be considered final.

ASSISTANCE WITH PUBLICATION

- For assistance with preparing manuscripts visit our **Online guide to scientific writing** at <http://www.cfa-international.org/ONGSWintro.html>

* Original means that the paper, or any close derivative of it, has not been published previously in any form, including on the internet.

Contents

PAPERS

Polycentric forest governance for social equity of Indigenous Peoples? A critical appraisal D. ADHIKARI	1	Unlocking the potential of private forests for carbon storage, biodiversity conservation, and livelihoods in Nepal R. JOSHI, H. ZHANG, T. MARASENI, N. DHAKAL, J. GAUTAM, H. SINGH and H. ADHIKARI	67
The transformation of institutional capacity for social forestry policy in Java, Indonesia M. ADIB, M. SAUD, R. RUSTINSYAH and I. ABDULLAH	16	Youth knowledge, engagement, and challenges in forest management and governance in Africa: a literature review C. WEKESA, A. ROOS, D. GITONGA, L. POPOOLA, D. MUTTA, M-L. AVANA-TIENTCHEU, C. MARK-HERBERT, F. BABALOLA, J. CHEBOIWO and P. MBILE	85
A comparative legal analysis of silvicultural interventions for sustainable forest management Ü. BİRBEN and F. ÇAKIR	29	Empirical analysis of the links between China's forest product imports and tropical forest loss X. SUN, A.L. HAMMETT and R. BUSH	102
An assessment of export-import performances of Nepal's wood sector: market landscape and trade indices analysis R.B. DANGI	42		
Energy forests on small rural properties in the semi-arid region of Brazil D.C. GAMA, D.A. DEUS, T.A.S. FREITAS, F.F. OLIVEIRA, M.D.S. FONSECA and A.C.P. SANTOS	55		
		BOOK REVIEW Resilient Forest Management <i>Philip J. Burton</i>	113

The transformation of institutional capacity for social forestry policy in Java, Indonesia

M. ADIB^a, M. SAUD^b, R. RUSTINSYAH^a and I. ABDULLAH^c

^a*Department of Anthropology, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia*

^b*Department of Sociology, Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Airlangga, Indonesia*

^c*Department of Anthropology, Faculty of Humanities, Universitas Gadjah Mada, Indonesia*

Email: moh.adib@fisip.unair.ac.id, muhammad.saud@fisip.unair.ac.id, rustinsyah@fisip.unair.ac.id, irwan.fib@ugm.ac.id

HIGHLIGHTS

- The 2014–2023 institutional transformation of social forestry (SF) in Java marked a strategic shift from state-centric control toward community-based management.
- Policy evolution progressed through three distinct stages: initiation (political vision), institutionalization (structural creation), and stabilization (legal consolidation).
- Intense public resistance and legal lawsuits during the stabilization stage revealed a critical gap between top-down regulations and grassroots expectations.
- While the transformation was systematically structured in official documents, it remains a ‘paper-based’ change that lacks robust implementation at the field level.
- The 2024 ministerial decoupling of forestry and environment served as a pivotal turning point to address previous bureaucratic stagnation and policy resistance.

SUMMARY

This paper examined regulators’ institutional capacity in transforming Java’s forest management through social forestry (SF) policy. Motivated by massive public resistance and lawsuits against the 2022 Forest Area with Special Management (KHDPK) policy, this study employed thematic content analysis of official documents (2014–2023). The research identified three transformative stages: initiation (*Nawacita* vision), institutionalization (PSKL Directorate establishment), and stabilization (Job Creation Law and KHDPK). Findings revealed that despite systematic legal structuring, transformation remains trapped in a state-centric paradigm, prioritizing internal bureaucratic consolidation over substantive community-based management. Failure to adapt to stakeholder needs has triggered policy stagnation. The study acknowledges the 2024 ministerial restructuring as a critical turning point for future research to evaluate whether the new institutional dichotomy can overcome previous bureaucratic failures.

Keywords: institutional capacity, social forestry policy, forest management transformation, public resistance, Java

INTRODUCTION

The institutional transformation of social forestry (SF) management in Indonesia, which was designed to move towards community-based management (2014–2023), has stagnated and sparked massive public controversy in Java (Adib *et al.* 2024a). This stagnation occurred because the reform efforts undertaken by the government through the merger of ministries into the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (2014) tended to focus on integration and internal bureaucratic restructuring, but failed to adapt effectively to the external environment and stakeholder demands in the field (Widiyanto *et al.* 2025, Purwanti *et al.* 2023). This is clear in the three stages of institutional change – initiation (the *Nawacita* idea), institutionalization (the formation of the Directorate General of PSKL), and stabilization (the issuance of laws 11/2020 and KHDPK) – which in practice only transferred control of

forest area management from one state-owned enterprise (Perum Perhutani) to another (KLHK). Ultimately, the stabilization policy through the Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry No. P. 287/2022 concerning Forest Areas with Special Management (KHDPK) in Java was strongly opposed by thousands of demonstrations, petitions of rejection, and lawsuits at the State Administrative Court (PTUN) (Adib *et al.* 2024a). Therefore, the Institutional Capacity Transformation that occurred during this period demonstrates that the paradigm shift from state-centric to community-centric has failed to be substantively realized and remains trapped within a centralized state control scheme.

The SF policy in Java has been in place since the Dutch colonial era (1873), and modern implementation only began in the 1970s (Pujo *et al.* 2018, Rahayu *et al.* 2024, Fisher *et al.* 2018). In that era, studies were generally conducted that focused on social aspects (Nurfatriani *et al.* 2023, Ramadhan

et al. 2025), economics (Rakatama and Pandit 2020, Piabuo *et al.* 2025, Hidayat, Bahruni, and Trison 2025), and ecology (Santika *et al.* 2019). However, research specifically addressing institutional aspects and institutional capacity building is rare, creating a crucial knowledge gap. This gap occurs because most studies tend to analyze SF from the perspective of impacts and outcomes at the site level (Supriyanto *et al.* 2024, Santika *et al.* 2019), while there is a lack of attention to policy mechanisms, the dynamics of regulatory structures, and the underlying transformational processes. Furthermore, regulators' failure to prepare adequate monitoring and evaluation mechanisms (Budi *et al.* 2021) often reflects a lack of interest in strengthening forest management capabilities, including critical dimensions such as human resource capacity (Lawasi 2024) and technology (Chandra *et al.* 2025). Therefore, research on institutional capacity transformation is crucial to providing a more comprehensive understanding of the successes and failures of SF programs within the broader context of public policy.

This study aimed to explain the institutional transformation of SF in Java (Adib and Rustinsyah 2025, Adib 2025). Although formulated systematically from 2014 to 2023 (Widiyanto *et al.* 2025), the process failed to shift the paradigm from state control to community-based management. This failure was evidenced by public resistance to the stabilization policy (KHDPK) (Adib *et al.* 2024a). The reasons for this failure were driven, among other things, by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry's (KLHK) regulator's focus on internal consolidation and institutional restructuring (through three stages: initiation, institutionalization, and stabilization). Internal consolidation was carried out while ignoring the need for adaptation to the external environment and stakeholder participation (Adib *et al.* 2024a). This is evident in the transformation process, which practically only transferred forest management authority from one state-owned enterprise (Perum Perhutani) to another state agency (KLHK), with a more centralized management system through the establishment of the Indicative Map and SF Area (PIAPS) since 2016 (Widiyanto *et al.* 2025, Rahayu *et al.* 2024). This study sought to uncover the roots of structural and institutional problems that cause programs intended for social justice and sustainability to end in controversy and innovation stagnation.

The institutional transformation of SF in Java (2014–2023) resulted only in the transfer of authority from one state agency to another (Perum Perhutani to the Ministry of Environment and Forestry), rather than a community-based paradigm shift (Widiyanto *et al.* 2025). This occurred because, in the process, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, as the new regulator, focused too much on completing internal institutional integration, such as developing internal regulations and performance structures, thus neglecting communication (C. Nugroho *et al.* 2025) and adapting to the external environment and the needs of forestry stakeholders in Java. This shift in authority took place through three stages: initiation (the *Nawacita* initiative), institutionalization (the establishment of the Directorate General of PSKL and PIAPS), and stabilization (the ratification of the Job Creation Law No. 11/2020 and the Ministerial Decree No. 287/2022 concerning KHDPK)

(Adib *et al.* 2024a). Although this legal framework appears robust and systematic in the documents, the implementation of the KHDPK stabilization policy has sparked strong public opposition, including demonstrations, petitions, and lawsuits before the State Administrative Court. Thus, this institutional transformation of SF has become merely a centralized administrative change, confirming that the policy remains under a rigid state control system and fails to meet the expectations of local communities.

Transformation of institutional capacity

The transformation of institutional capacity in managing forest areas in Java urgently needs to be discussed, not only within the island but also in the region of ASEAN countries (Wong *et al.* 2020). The institutional capacity transformation involves a series of steps taken to strengthen the capabilities of an organization into two major dimensions, i.e., strengthening human resource capacity and technological resources in the form of information technology infrastructure (Pujo *et al.* 2018).

The transformation of institutional capacity in forest area management in Java demonstrated that, the formulation of policy and regulatory evaluation through institutional analysis, community participation, analysis of inter-agency cooperation, and capacity development (Uda *et al.* 2020, Rahayu *et al.* 2024, Kailola *et al.* 2023) is essential for bridging the gap between national mandates and local implementation. Through the identification of implementation weaknesses and obstacles (Carson *et al.* 2018), this policy evaluation mechanism introduces more effective, inclusive, and sustainable regulations (Adib *et al.* 2024a, Adib *et al.* 2024b). By addressing these challenges, the framework ensures that future regulatory adjustments are grounded in empirical field realities rather than purely administrative ideals.

The institutional analysis describes the institutions' structure and dynamics, including roles, responsibilities, and interactions between relevant parties (stakeholders) in the policy-making environment (regulators), operators and forest care communities. Active participation by local forest communities in planning and decision-making processes is crucial for the successful implementation of forest policies and long-term sustainability. Moreover, analyzing cooperation among institutions by strengthening social networks focuses on preserving forests (Garrett *et al.* 2021). Therefore, transforming institutional capacity in the management of forest areas in Java holds great importance and requires the attention of academia and policymaking by improving the capacities of relevant institutions, involving local communities, and building strong collaboration towards sustainable forest management and more effective land conservation in Java.

Social forestry: operationalization of agrarian reform policy

Social forestry (SF) is sustainable forest management carried out in state forest areas or privately operated forests by the engagement of local communities and the implementation of

customary laws as the main actors to improve welfare, environmental balance, and socio-cultural dynamics (Nancy Lee Peluso 1993, Zulkarnain 2021). This community-based sustainable forest management (Rakatama and Pandit 2020) continues the agrarian reform policy, which was established to restructure resource ownership, control and consumption (Zakaria et al. 2018). This management system is seen as progressive in the interest of the people associated with forest areas (Murti 2018, Peluso and Poffenberger 1989). SF policy continues to develop internationally with four formal objectives, namely institutional, social, environmental, and economic (Rakatama and Pandit 2020).

SF policy is a series of agrarian reform policies designed to ensure the legality of assets and land redistribution to the main actors participating in forest management within a legal structure (Supriyanto et al. 2021). The Ministry of Environment and Forestry Regulation No. 83/2016 establishes the legal framework for SF, setting a national target for SF areas at 12.7 million hectares (Pambudi 2020). Specifically in the region of Java, the functional area of the state-owned forestry sector, Perhutani, has been in place since the enactment of Regulation P. 39 of 2017, covering an area of approximately 1.1 million hectares (Pane et al. 2021). As soon as the regulation was published, there was a substantial public response which was not only controversial, narrating both pros and cons (Ramadhan and Amalia 2021, Pane, Yanis, and Susanto 2021), but also contradictory (Wibowo, Race, and Curtis 2013, Rakatama and Pandit 2020).

Alongside these regulatory changes, institutional reforms have been implemented to strengthen the governance of forest management in Java. Most of these studies on this issue have discussed social, economic, and ecological aspects (Siscawati 2013, Fisher et al. 2018, Rakatama and Pandit 2020, Fisher et al. 2018). It is still rare to find studies that discuss institutional aspects and capacity building on SF. This institutional aspect explains the pros and cons of structuring forest management in Java. Ultimately, this institutional gap highlights regulators' failure to fulfill their mandates, primarily due to the absence of robust monitoring and evaluation mechanisms (Sunarso 2022).

To date, monitoring and evaluation of social forestry have failed to focus on the strategic roles of regulators, particularly the Ministry, which appears less prioritized in institutional strengthening efforts (Pujo et al. 2018). This lack of focus is critical because effective forest management requires a balanced development of both human resource capacities and technological infrastructure to ensure policy targets are met. As such, strengthening the human resource capacity as part and section of institutional capacity transformation should involve three aspects: the transformation process, factors influencing transformation, and transformation models. The process of transformation of institutional capacity focuses on the establishment and formation of institutions, community empowerment (Jopang, Tunda, and Tarifu 2022, Tàbara et al. 2018), liaising partnerships, capacity building (Langseth et al. 2023), and the mechanism of monitoring and evaluation (Iriyani et al. 2020).

Valuable lessons can be learned from studying the experiences of other countries that have incorporated SF within their agrarian reform programs. For example, in Brazil and Denmark, SF was implemented as a direct continuation of agrarian reform policies to ensure social equity (Robles 2018, Boberg-Fazlić et al. 2022). Similarly, the Chinese government targeted landscape governance through systematic implementation (Zhang 2019), while Sweden's approach involved over two decades of institutional stabilization (Pemer and Skjølsvik 2018). Gaining insights from these diverse international experiences provides essential benchmarks for the execution and implementation of SF policy in Indonesia.

METHODS

This study employed a qualitative approach with thematic content analysis to explore the transformation of institutional capacity within SF policies in Java from 2014 to 2023. The research focused on the paradigm shift in forest management – moving from a state-centric model toward community involvement – through three transformative phases: initiation, institutionalization, and stabilization. Primary data sources were gathered from official regulatory documents, government policy reports, and scientific publications relevant to the *Nawacita* vision and the implementation of Forest Area with Special Management (KHDPK). The data were analyzed using a systematic five-stage coding technique, progressing from initial identification to final verification, to translate regulatory texts into a concrete narrative of institutional change. The systematic research workflow, encompassing data input, the multi-stage analysis process, and the synthesis of findings, is illustrated in the following flowchart.

This study was qualitative research with a descriptive approach focusing on thematic content analysis to explore the transformation of institutional capacity within SF policies in Java. The scope of this research covered the period from 2014 to 2023, specifically examining the shift in forest management paradigm from a state-centric model toward community involvement through three transformative stages: initiation, institutionalization, and stabilization. The primary geographical focus was the working areas of Perum Perhutani across four provinces in Java (See Map), namely Central Java, East Java, West Java, and Banten.

As a content analysis study, the participants in this research did not refer to individuals as direct informants, but rather to policy and regulatory documents issued by regulatory institutions as the units of observation. The primary data sources were derived from official documents of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MoEF), government policy reports, and scientific publications related to the transformation of SF in Indonesia. The document selection criteria were based on online accessibility, relevance to the *Nawacita* vision, institutional strengthening (Directorate General of PSKL), and implementing regulations such as the Job Creation Law Number 11/2020 and the ministerial decree on KHDPK (SK 287/2022).

FIGURE 1 Flow Chart of the Research Method

The primary instrument in this study was the researcher as the key instrument, assisted by Mendeley reference management software to organize and classify the data. Additionally, data extraction tables were employed as instruments to filter essential information, such as keywords (*Nawacita*, conflict resolution, community welfare), strategic phrases (President’s vision and mission, community participation), and abstract concepts (paradigm shifts, public resistance). These instruments ensured that all data were systematically documented in accordance with the institutional capacity transformation framework.

Data collection was conducted through digital documentation studies from July to September 2023 by accessing official government databases and scientific journal repositories. The collection process followed strict document filtration stages to ensure the relevance of the texts to the policy phases under study. The collected data included legal regulations, strategic plans (Renstra of the Directorate General of PSKL 2015–2019), Indicative Maps of SF Areas (PIAPS), and data related to public resistance, such as lawsuits in the Administrative Court (PTUN) that emerged during the policy stabilization stage.

Data analysis was conducted using thematic content analysis consisting of five systematic steps: comprehensive document collection, repetitive reading and initial coding, grouping codes into major themes, data extraction into tables, and final verification. The data were categorized into three main phases: initiation (*Nawacita* vision), institutionalization (establishment of the Directorate General of PSKL), and stabilization (formalization through the Job Creation Law and KHDPK policy). Specifically, during the stabilization stage, the analysis was expanded to include data on public resistance, such as documentation of demonstrations, rejection petitions, and legal lawsuits in the Administrative Court (PTUN). The inclusion of resistance data is crucial to verify whether the institutional capacity transformation, which appears administratively robust in policy documents, aligns with field-level acceptance. This analytical flow aimed to reveal the contradictions between regulatory progress and substantive implementation barriers that trigger obstacles in policy stabilization.

RESULTS

The transformation of forest area management in Java from state-based to community-based has been implemented through the SF program in three stages: initiation, institutionalization, and stabilization. These stages were implemented through the structuring and implementation of statutory regulations. Moreover, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK), Indonesia, offers to enforce rules in the SF policy.

The initiation stage (2014–2015): *Nawacita* and the vision for social forestry

The initial stage of SF was proposed by President Joko Widodo when he was running for the presidential candidacy in 2014. This agenda of change was portrayed in the vision, mission, and campaign platform known as *Nawacita* Jokowi (Vision and mission). The vision and mission of Jokowi were intended to allow the people to achieve a politically sovereign, economically independent, and culturally diverse Indonesia. As such, *Nawacita* has a vision of organizing change into nine agendas (Table 1). Among three of the nine agendas, the first, sixth, and seventh were focused on or related to forest management. The first agenda was designed to strengthen the state system with reforms and law enforcement that could be dignified, trustworthy and free from corruption. The sixth agenda aimed to increase people’s capabilities and skills to meet international standards. The seventh agenda was focused on economic independence by targeting strategic sectors of the domestic economy (Widodo and Kalla 2014, Ditjen PSKL KLHK RI 2016). The initiation stage of this institutional arrangement was also carried out by merging two ministries (Tables 1 and 2) by the President of the Republic of Indonesia (KLHK) (Table 1). Thus, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry prepared a strategic plan for 2015–2019 in this regard (Table 1).

TABLE 1 *Social Forestry Program through Vision and Mission (Nawacita) in 2014*

No.	Initiation of the Formation of Social Forestry Institutions	Basic Regulations / Legislation / Ideas	Source
1.	<i>Nawacita</i> is a policy of the Joko Widodo and Jusuf Kalla administration to realize community welfare starting from the outskirts. The main objective of the <i>Nawacita</i> program is to improve the lives and welfare of the community, quality of life of the Indonesian people through Agrarian Reforms. The target of agrarian reform is abandoned Land Use Rights (LUR) and barren lands to be redistributed to farm workers, while also providing legalization for state lands	Joko Widodo's speech in the Presidential Campaign in the 2014 Indonesian Presidential Election	(Widodo and Kalla. 2014, Widodo <i>et al.</i> 2018)
2.	Article 4 (ii). The Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnerships; ... (Article 30), ... The Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnerships has the task of formulating and implementing policies in increasing community participation in forest management, handling customary forests, and environmental partnerships.	Presidential Regulation (PERPRES) No. 16 of 2015 concerning the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (Article 4 (i) and Article 30)	(Presiden RI. 2015, Presiden RI. 2020)
3.	Regulation of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, Indonesia Number P.39/Menlhk-Setjen/2015 concerning the Strategic Plan for 2015–2019.	Strategic Plan of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry for 2015–2019	(Menteri LHK. 2015, Menteri LHK. 2020)

The institutionalization stage (2015–2019): structural integration within the MOEF

The President and the Minister of Environment and Forestry planned the institutional transformation in SF. The President established SF institutions by merging two ministries into one, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). In KLHK, article 4 (i), the Directorate General of SF and Environmental Management (Ditjen PSKL) was established (Table 2). In establishing the PSKL institution, the Ministry of Environment and Forestry focused on three steps for completing the institutional structure of the PSKL Directorate General including the scope of roles, responsibilities and functions for 2013–2017 (Table 2), preparation of the Strategic Plan (*Renstra*) of the Directorate General of PSKL, Ministry of Environment and Forestry for 2015–2019 (Table 2), and to determine a map of the area of forest areas in Java in an indicative SF map (PIAPS). Thus, during these changes, PIAPS underwent its 7th revision in 2016 (Table 2), indicating SF in a yielded area in 2017.

Forestry operations in Java cover forest areas of four provinces, including Central Java, East Java, West Java, and Banten (Table 2). This policy, implemented by the President and the Minister of Environment and Forestry, has become the legal basis for determining the SF policy in the work of *Perum Perhutani* in four provinces in Java. However, among these four provinces, only Yogyakarta (a special region) is not managed by the *Perum Perhutani*.

The stabilization stage (since 2020): the Job Creation Law and KHDPK implementation

The stabilization of SF policy implemented by the President emphasized legal certainty by enacting Law number 11/2020, Government Regulation (PP) 23/2021 (see Table 3). According

to policy 11/2020 articles No. 29A and 29B, the SF program focuses on the sustainability and protection of forest areas. A giant forest area was given to individual farmers, forest farmer groups, and companies pursuing business permits. In policy document 23 of 21, article 108 para (1) and para (2), the implementation of forestry for various purposes is defined as a forest area with special management determined by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry.

The respective Ministry, based on these two legal frameworks, then issued a Decree (Kepmen LHK) SK.8878/2021 concerning Indicative Maps and SF Areas (PIAPS) revision VII (see Table 3). After a year, SK 9978/2021 was followed by with Decree Number 287/2022 concerning Forest Areas with Special Management (KHDPK) in Java covering Central Java Province, East Java Province, West Java Province, and Banten Province. Since 2020, the SF program was started through the stipulation of legislation, implementing regulations by the President, and two technical rules by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, as a basis for structuring the forest area management in Java, except Yogyakarta.

DISCUSSION

The three stages of institutional transformation have established their legal frameworks through the legislation and regulations implemented in Java. However, the Ministry further stipulates policies and rules for implementation at the stabilization stage. The special implementing regulations on the island of Java issued a decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry number 287 related to Forest Areas with Special Management (KHDPK). However, the public resisted the decree P. 287 circulated by the concerned Ministry of Indonesia.

TABLE 2 Institutionalization of Social Forestry from 2015–2017

No.	Establishment of Social Forestry Institutions	Basic Regulations/Legislation	Sources
1.	Presidential Decree Number 16 of 2015 concerning the Ministry of Environment and Forestry's duties (Article 2) status revoked and replaced with Presidential Decree 92/2020 regarding the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, CHAPTER II ORGANIZATION, Part One Organizational Structure "...Article 6 (i) Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnership."	Presidential Decree Number 16 of 2015 concerning the Ministry of Environment and Forestry's duties (Article 2) status revoked and replaced with Presidential Decree 92/2020 regarding the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, CHAPTER II ORGANIZATION, Part One Organizational Structure	(Presiden RI. 2015) is revoked and replaced with (Presiden RI. 2020a)
2.	"..... after the merger of the organization and work procedures of the directorates by the Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry Number P.18/MenLHK-II/2015 concerning the Organization and Work Procedures of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry. According to Article 1005, the Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnerships has the task of formulating and implementing policies in the field of increasing community participation in forest management, handling customary forests, and environmental partnerships." "..... to carry out its duties and functions, as regulated in Article 1007, its organizational structure consists of; (1) Secretariat of the Directorate General; (2) Directorate of Preparation of Social Forestry Areas; (3) Directorate of Handling Conflict, Tenure, and Customary Law; (4) Directorate of Social Forestry and Customary Forest Business Development; and (5) Directorate of Environmental Partnerships."	Establishment of the Directorate of Social Forestry and Environmental Management, Organizational Structure and Scope at the Directorate General of PSKL 2013–2017	(Sambodo 2015, Ditjen PSKL KLHK. 2015:4)
3.	"Ministry of Environment and Forestry Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnership. Regulation of the Director General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnership Number: P. 11/Pskl – Setdit/2015 Concerning the Strategic Plan of the Directorate General of Social Forestry and Environmental Partnership for 2015–2019"	Rencana Strategis Ditjen PSKL Kementerian LHK (2015–2019). Strategic Plan of the Directorate General of PSKL, Ministry of Environment and Forestry (2015–2019)	(Ditjen PSKL KLHK. 2015)
4.	Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia "Number P.83/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/10/2016 Concerning Social Forestry" "Number 39 of 2017 concerning Social Forestry in the Working Area of Perum Perhutani"	Regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia Number P.83/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/10/2016 Concerning Social Forestry. Number P.39/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/6/2017 concerning Social Forestry in Perhutani Working Areas.	(Men LHK. 2016, Men LHK. 2017)

The vision and mission (*Nawacita*) is the idea of Presidential Candidate (*Capres*) Joko Widodo (Table 1), which was put forward at the launch of the campaign to run for the presidential nomination in 2014 (Hastangka 2020), not only as a mandate that covers direction and strategy in the forestry sector (Hastangka 2020, Zulkarnain 2021, Utomo 2021), but also as a translation of agrarian reform and Indonesia's development strategy from the periphery, starting from the grassroots level (Pambudi 2020, Supriyanto *et al.* 2021, Zulkarnain 2021). These Agrarian Reforms were then designated as a national priority to improve community welfare (Waryanta 2016, Aldillah 2020). As such, agrarian reforms

are the basis for initiating the SF program as an embodiment of *Nawacita* and for identifying other potential forest areas. These areas were considered barren land, therefore, the government declared these areas through Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 86/2018 as land for agrarian reform (TORA).

The Minister of Environment and Forestry identified and highlighted the TORA program in the form of land redistribution (Wicaksono *et al.* 2019). Moreover, the TORA is an implementation of *Nawacita* focusing on nine million hectares of forest area (Aldillah 2020), to utilize the areas that were no longer productive in improving welfare and creating social

TABLE 3 *Stabilization of Social Forestry Programs through Legislation 2020–2022*

No.	Stabilization of Social Forestry Programs	Basic Regulations / Legislation / Implementation Provisions	Source
1.	<p>“Article 29A. (1) Utilization of protected forests and production forests, as referred to in Article 26 and Article 28, may be carried out for social forestry activities. (2) Social forestry, as referred to in paragraph (1), may be given to: a. individuals; b. forest farmer groups; and c. cooperatives.”</p> <p>“Article 29B. Further provisions regarding business licensing for forest utilization and social forestry activities are regulated by government regulation.”</p>	Law Number 11 of 2020 concerning Job Creation Articles 29A and 29B	(Presiden RI. 2020b)
2.	<p>Article 108 paragraphs (1) and (2);</p> <p>“Part Three Forest Areas with Specific Purposes. Paragraph 1 (General).</p> <p>Article 108. (1) For specific purposes, Forest Areas may be designated as: a. Forest Areas with specific purposes; b. Forest Areas with special management; or c. Forest Areas for food security. (2) The Minister shall make the determination as referred to in paragraph (1).”</p> <p>Article 125 paragraphs (1), (7),</p> <p>“(1) The Central Government may delegate the implementation of Forest management to state-owned enterprises in the Forestry sector.”</p> <p>“(7) For Protected Forest Areas and Production Forest Areas that are not delegated the implementation of Forestry as referred to in paragraph (2), their management shall be delegated to state-owned enterprises in the field of being designated as Forest Areas with Forest Area management in the context of the Establishment of Special Areas for the interests of Social Forestry, Forest Arrangement and Forest Area Arrangement in the context of Utilization of Forest Areas, Use of Forest Areas, Forest Rehabilitation or Utilization of Environmental Services which are the authority of the Central Government.”</p>	Government Regulation no. 23 of 2021 concerning Forestry Implementation Article 108 paragraphs (1) and (2); Article 125 paragraphs (1), (7)	(Presiden RI. 2021)
3.	“Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia No. SK.8878/MENLHK-PKTL/REN/PLA.0/12/21 Concerning Indicative Maps and Social Forestry Areas Revision VII”	Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia No. SK.8878/MENLHK-PKTL/REN/PLA.0/12/21 Concerning Indicative Maps and Social Forestry Areas Revision VII	(Men LHK. 2021, Men LHK. 2021)
4.	“Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia No. SK.287/MENLHK/SETJEN/PLA.2/4/2022 concerning Determination of Forest Areas with Special Management in Parts of State Forests in Production Forest and Protected Forest Areas in Central Java Province, East Java Province, West Java Province, Banten Province.”	Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry of the Republic of Indonesia No. SK.287/MENLHK/SETJEN/PLA.2/4/2022 concerning Determination of Forest Areas with Special Management in Parts of State Forests in Production Forest and Protected Forest Areas in Central Java Province, East Java Province, West Java Province, Banten Province.	(Men LHK. 2022)

and economic justice for the community (Nugroho *et al.* 2021). The goal of agrarian reform from an institutional perspective has also faced criticism (Aldillah 2020) due to its top-down approach and lack of clarity in its implementation. Moreover, the TORA locations determined by the Ministry

were not only the targeted forest areas but also many agrarian conflicts and even conflicting community claims over forest areas. The criticism of TORA policy as a basic framework for institutional structuring of the SF program emphasizes the need for revisions.

The implementation of agrarian reform in Java differs significantly from the experiences reported in the literature concerning Brazil and Denmark. Agrarian reform in Brazil, driven by farmers for more than three decades since 1985, has had only a limited impact on changing the situation (Robles 2018). In this movement, Agrarian reform was still treated as a political promise by the elite, but the political elite could not shift the dominance of agribusiness. The democratic government in Brazil has encouraged the opening of new land frontiers by providing significant economic incentives (Hershaw and Sauer 2023). The land redistribution has been balanced by further land ownership. In response to this policy, investors weakened agrarian reforms efforts and opened up a dependency on the agricultural economy, which is sensitive in a social and environmental context. In these circumstances, the political and economic crises that occurred in Brazil have increasingly eroded the struggle for agrarian reforms. In Denmark, it was designed and portrayed as a pro-market and pro-farmer policy in the 18th century, which increased inequality (Boberg-Fazlić *et al.* 2022). The gap in land ownership is based on land type, which has increased in areas classified as productive. As a result, many regions have disproportionately received surpluses, whereas, in other places, poor people are emulated to rural areas. Although in a different period, agrarian reforms experienced in these two countries compared to Indonesia, even though it started with an initiation action in 2014, has shown a step forward with the designation of land as an objective of agrarian reform (TORA).

The institutionalization of SF in continuation to the initiation stage was executed with the establishment of the Directorate General of SF and Environmental Management (Ditjen PSKL). This PSKL represents an increase in responsibility status to echelon I level (Directorate General), which was previously under a work unit equivalent to echelon II. This increase in institutional status requires the Ministry of Environment and Forestry to abide by internal improvements and regulate the policies that support the directions given by the President (Pambudi 2020). The formation of the Directorate General of PSKL is a response to the implementation of agrarian reform, which has faced various challenges. The challenges in institutional improvements include consolidating strong regulations, licensing updates, human resource qualifications, budget allocations, updating coordination, policies, and joint ownership with the local governments (Ayuningutami and Najicha 2022). The institutional improvements and internal consolidation are also intended to achieve the target of 20% (approximately 4.2 million hectares) of the 12.7 million hectare area from 2015 to 2019 (Fisher *et al.* 2018, Pambudi 2020, Pane *et al.* 2021). Launching the SF permit involves several steps, including the regional government and community-based organization (CSOs). The limited internal capacity also triggers conflict. The conflict occurs when the community feels the SF policy does not align with the existing guidelines. And there is no legal certainty in managing forest areas around their settlements (Pane *et al.* 2021). Thus, more substantial legal certainty in the form of a law is needed to stabilize the SF program.

Furthermore, the Chinese government has also launched an institutional improvement program in line with efforts to achieve environmental development targets through landscape management policies and landscape governance systematically by linking six inseparable elements (Zhang 2019). These six elements include improving conflict resolution, which has implications for social and ecological environmental problems, increasing the capacity of state administrators in landscape management, developing new land use management systems with good ecological security and broader ecosystem services, providing more significant public benefit to the landscape, developing civil society and democracy, and structuring the landscape architecture education and research curriculum. These elements of governance change the conventional paradigm of landscape as an 'ecological environment' into an institutional system of 'ecological civilization.' Thus, strengthening the institutions of ecological civilization has also been directed at various dimensions of education and research in landscape architecture. Further, institutional analysis is also introduced in courses such as the sociology of landscape in educational institutions. The discussion in these courses focuses on the influence of social institutions, laws and regulations, policies related to the landscape, and the applicability of rules and regulations. The institutional improvements are also based on the experiences of China, which have been launched systemically, including structuring the curriculum in formal activities such as through education and research.

The establishment of a legal framework through legislation, even though it has a strong position as institutional stabilization of the SF program, is seen as a tenure that guarantees certainty and boom in businesses of forest areas. The institutional stabilization to improve more technical forest management mechanisms can be done by strengthening managerial skills to reduce disparities by encouraging community forest management (Rakatama and Pandit 2020, Wollenberg *et al.* 2007). Besides, this strong structure of legal certainty has become an important legal milestone for the stakeholders so that they may not be evicted from the designated areas when implementing the SF program (Syanurisma 2022). However, efforts to overcome the gap between expectations and reality have reportedly faced five challenges. Firstly, SF activities are still under a strict state control scheme through administrative procedures and bureaucratic design (Adib 2025), making the forest management system ineffective and increasing operational costs. Secondly, contesting forest area management rights leads to conflict between community members. Thirdly, the SF schemes have an unequal distribution of rights and responsibilities. Fourthly, unfair compensation for the contributions made by each stakeholder, SF is often still viewed within the framework of the interests of each stakeholder. And lastly, local village elites receive forest concessions more as compared to the ordinary village residents. These differences in getting concessions give rise to internal conflicts between local village communities. In line with managerial weaknesses in implementing this forestry program, FAO research in 2015 conducted on 23 countries found out that only three

countries had provided SF provisions in their forestry laws. However, there is lack of implementation (Aggarwal *et al.* 2021). The institutional stabilization for strengthening legalities is insufficient to effectively implement SF policy, which requires strong management skills at various levels and in the field.

A longitudinal study conducted by Pemer and Skjølvsvik (2018) in Sweden regarding the implementation of new regulations involving institutional work found that the regulatory implementation process was carried out through four waves: the initial impact as a result of institutional shocks (1994–1999), the response (2000–2004), recovery (2004–2008), and the stabilization (2009–2013). The first wave describes the dissemination of information in the field. In the second wave, the response dealt with navigating a new institutional landscape. In the third wave, the public procurement/service landscape remained fragmented. Meanwhile, in the wave of stabilization, public organizations and local businesses collaborated to encourage dialogue and the development of public services. In each wave, different bureaucratic, market, and professional techniques were used, but the regulators also implemented top-down hierarchical institutional activities. These four waves follow sequential processes as the phases of institutional work relate to each other and give rise to new types of institutional work.

Therefore, implementing these new regulations is not always one-way but a two-way process of action and counteraction that moves forward until resolution. Sweden's experience shows that reaching the stabilization stage can take up to two decades; this requirement for policy stability offers a significant lesson for structuring policies in other regions.

Recent developments: The 2024 ministerial restructuring and its implications

The stabilization stage, which combined the two previous stages, initiation and institutionalization, was ineffective. The failure to structure forest area management in Java is not only marked by resistance from the public, with various rejections, lawsuits, and demands for revocation in the Court of Justice (PTUN) but also proved a failure in implementing changes in the established paradigm. The paradigm established in forest area management through SF from state-based to community-based practically shifted authority from one state (BUMN in the forestry sector Perhutani) to another state (Ministry of Environment and Forestry), with a more centralized management system by establishing Indicative Maps and SF Areas (PIAPS) since 2016 (Rakatama and Pandit 2020). Thus, the determination of PIAPS is revised every six months, the latest in 2023 being the 8th revision (MenLHK 2023). The Ministry of Environment and Forestry took over this forest area of 1.1 million and 2.4 million hectares in Java to manage it through the Forest Area with Special Management policy – KHDPK (Men LHK 2022). The shift in authority from one state to another, followed by massive resistance from the public, is a sign of the stagnation of innovation carried out by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry. This stagnation

occurred due to the failure to adapt to the external environment, which focused on structuring the internal integration of Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) institutions.

The first element is internal integration. In carrying out its duties, the bureaucracy of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) must concentrate on completing internal integration matters. Internal integration (Rosenberg 2020), carried out by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, deals with structuring internal regulations and performance in its institutions in three stages. The arrangement of legal rules has been uploaded on the official website since February 2017 (Ditjen PSKL KLHK 2017). The publication, launched by the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) at the Directorate General SF and Environmental Partnerships (Ditjen PSKL), includes the documents related to statutory regulations, Presidential regulations, Government regulations, Decree of the Minister of Environment and Forestry, regulation of the Minister of Environment and Forestry (Permen LHK), Decree (SK) of the Minister of Environment and Forestry, and Decree of the Directorate General of PSKL. A total of 15 regulations from 2015–2023, Minister of Environment and Forestry's Decree (SK) (3 SK 2016–2017), Minister of Environment and Forestry's Decree concerning PAPS revision 1 Per Province (10 provinces in 2017) and Decree of the Director General of PSKL (2017) concerning changes to the SF Working Group (POKJA PS). The publications prepared since 2015 are in the strategic plan of the Directorate General of PSKL 2015–2019, Directorate of SF Area Preparation (Dit PKPS), Directorate of SF Business Development and Customary Law (Dit BUPSHA), Directorate of Conflict Management, Tenurial and Customary Forests (Dit PKTHA), Directorate of Environmental Partnerships (Dit KL), SF and Environmental Partnership Center (BPSKL) strategic plan for Sumatra, Java Bali Nusa Tenggara, Kalimantan, Sulawesi, Maluku Papua 2015–2019. The work plan and performance report (2018 to 2023) and the publication of the 2023 document are up to the budget and performance program of the Ditjen of PSKL (KLHK 2023). This focus on completing internal integration has forgotten an inseparable part of the KLHK's duties as a regulator: adapting to the external environment (Fatem *et al.* 2018, Klein *et al.* 2019) for forest area management stakeholders in Java. Thus, the stakeholders managing forest areas in Java (Perhutani), environmental NGOs, and LMDH (Forest Village Community Institutions) at the local, regional, and national levels.

Secondly, the institutional transformation, which emphasizes structuring internal integration within the Ministry of Environment and Forestry, does not necessarily reduce stakeholders' ability to adapt to the changes in the external environment. The external environment in managing forest areas in Java is undergoing multiple changes, including climate change, environmental observers and researchers, community demands, the Perhutani, and non-governmental organizations. The flexibility in responding to change is a challenge for innovative action in maintaining sustainable forest area management. The flexibility of innovative actions is oriented towards building solid partnerships between KLHK regulators and stakeholders, strengthening strong multi-actor partnerships, and

encouraging innovation in adapting to environmental changes. Additionally, the regulators drive stakeholders' collaboration as a structural component of the innovation system of the organizations. Fieldsend and colleagues (2022) examined 200 European partnerships involving farmers and foresters. As a result, the innovation process and stakeholders successfully determined the structure that is more appropriate for specific stakeholders given the circumstances. The influential factors in this regard include actor capacity, aspirations, and networks. Furthermore, the discussion encompasses the topic of co-innovation, its influence on partnership size and work plan structure, the types of activities, and the need to engage with 'larger fringe groups' within the supporting environment.

Third, the institutional landscape of Indonesian forestry underwent a seismic shift in late 2024 with the dissolution of the integrated Ministry of Environment and Forestry (MOEF) and the re-establishment of a standalone Ministry of Forestry (Rahmi *et al.* 2025). This restructuring represents a critical response to the bureaucratic 'overload' and policy stagnation identified during the 2014–2023 period (Ekowanti *et al.* 2025). While the previous integrated model aimed for synergistic land management, the findings of this study suggest that it often resulted in internal consolidation. This process prioritized state-centric administrative control rather than community-centric empowerment.

The new dichotomy – separating forestry's production and conservation functions from environmental oversight – offers a dual-edged sword for SF in Java. On the one hand, it provides the Ministry of Forestry with an opportunity to specialize its institutional capacity and streamline the implementation of KHDPK without the burden of overlapping environmental mandates. On the other hand, it risks resurrecting old 'sectoral egos' and coordination barriers that could further delay the resolution of public resistance and legal disputes. Ultimately, the success of this 2024 transformation will depend on whether the new Ministry can move beyond 'paper-based' legalism and foster a more inclusive, equal partnership model as a core strategy for forest governance (Adib *et al.* 2024b).

CONCLUSION

The present study discussed the SF policy in Java, Indonesia, which the government of President Joko Widodo institutionally transformed. The SF policy has not changed from its original form, although the President can change or revise it. The institutional transformation through the initiation, institutionalization, and stabilization stages is simply shifting the implementation of forestry in Java from Perum Perhutani to the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK) through the Directorate General of SF and Environmental Management (Ditjen PSKL). The SF policy is still under the control of the state paradigm in management, which is more centralized. The centralization of forest area management in SF can be seen as a scheme which ensures that land and forest resources are under the strict control of the state through various administrative procedures and bureaucratic structures.

This state-based management scheme is equivalent to the management carried out by Perum Perhutani from the 1970s to 2014.

The concept of institutional capacity transformation used in this research reveals three main stages for forest area management: initiation, institutionalization and stabilization. Mr. Joko Widodo carried out the initiation stage of the SF program during his 2014 presidential candidacy campaign under *Nawacita*, the idea of which is a national vision used as a basis for the documents written in the 2015–2019 RPJMN. The institutionalization stage was carried out through Presidential Regulation (Perpres) Number 16 of 2015, which merged two ministries in the Ministry of Environment and Forestry (KLHK). Presidential Decree 16/2015 confirms the establishment of the Directorate General of SF and Social Management (Ditjen PSKL).

The Ministry of Environment and Forestry executed the institutionalization of the SF program in Java by establishing Indicative Maps and SF Areas (PIAPS) and its implementation in the working area of Perum Perhutani (P 39/2017). The stabilization stage of the SF program is strengthened in the Job Creation Law - UUCK (11/2020 articles 29A and 29B). In this UUCK, the term 'SF' was written explicitly in the legal system in Indonesia for the first time. Further, it concludes that, through the content analysis of the stages of policy determination, evaluation of institutional capacity transformation, and recommendations for community empowerment, this research makes a significant contribution to improving environmental sustainability, community welfare, sustainable resource management, community empowerment and achieving sustainable development goals as a whole. Thus, this research provides new insight for establishing more sustainable forest area management policies and more prosperous communities in and around forests.

The limitations of this research lie in its primary reliance on statutory documents and official technical provisions available through public domains, which may not fully capture the informal dynamics of institutional change. Furthermore, this study is bounded by the temporal context of 2014–2023, during which the forestry and environmental sectors were integrated under a single ministry (MOEF). The significant structural separation of these sectors into the Ministry of Forestry and the Ministry of Environment in late 2024 marks a new era that necessitates further investigation. Future research should transition from document-based analysis to longitudinal panel data surveys or ethnographic approaches to evaluate how this new institutional dichotomy influences the effectiveness of SF in Java, particularly in overcoming the public resistance and bureaucratic stagnation identified in this study.

GENERATIVE AI STATEMENT

During the preparation of this manuscript, the author used Scopus AI in order to validate data and verify key statements within the text. After using this tool, the author reviewed and edited the content as needed and took full responsibility for the content of the published article.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This research was conducted independently. The authors would like to thank the Dean of the Faculty of Social and Political Sciences, Universitas Airlangga, Surabaya, Indonesia, Prof. Dr. Bagong Suyanto, Drs., M.Si., who facilitated not only for providing the opportunity of Penelitian Unggulan Fakultas (PUF) with the number 1870 /UN3.1.7/PT/2021 but also the presentation of the main ideas of this article on 25–26 August 2023 at Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin (UniSZA) Terengganu, Malaysia in the 9th International Conference on Contemporary Social and Political Affairs (ICocSPA) on the theme ‘Hitting the Barriers: ASEAN Epicenter of Growth.’ The authors also thank the participants for their comments and input during the presentation. We also want to acknowledge Prof. Alan Pottinger, the editorial team of the International Forestry Review (IFR), and anonymous reviewers for their comments and suggestions to improve the quality of this paper.

DECLARATION OF INTEREST

The authors report no conflict of interest. The authors are responsible for the content and writing of this article.

REFERENCES

- ADIB, M. 2025. *Pidato pengukuhan: antropologi ekologi untuk perhutanan sosial di indonesia(mendesak keadilan lingkungan dan keberlanjutan hutan tropis)*. Pertama. Surabaya: Airlangga University Press.
- ADIB, M., ABDULLAH, I., ARTARIA, M.D., RUSTINSYAH, R., ASMOROWATI, S., WARDHANI, B., ROSNON, M.R., and MASHUD, M. 2024. The controversy of social forestry policy: public reaction on the Ministry of Environment and Forestry Decree No. 287/2022/KHDPK in Java, Indonesia. *Forest Science and Technology* **20**(4): 383–400. doi:10.1080/21580103.2024.2409212.
- ADIB, M., HENDRAWATI, L.D., and SANTOSO, P. 2024. Kolaborasi yang inklusif, membangun kemitraan yang setara dalam perhutanan sosial. Pp. 58–76 in *Menjaga Tradisi Membangun Itentias: Narasi Budaya di Era Digital*, edited by Anwari, I.R.M. Surabaya: SAGA.
- ADIB, M., and RUSTINSYAH, R. 2025. *Perhutanan sosial – konsep, praktik, serta dampaknya pada masyarakat dan lingkungan*. Pertama. Surabaya: Airlangga University Press.
- AGGARWAL, S., LARSON, A., MCDERMOTT, C., KATILA, P., and GIESSEN, L. 2021. Tenure reform for better forestry: an unfinished policy agenda. *Forest Policy and Economics* **123**: 102376. doi:10.1016/j.forpol.2020.102376.
- ALDILLAH, R. 2020. Dynamics of the tora program at 2015–2019 period in Indonesia agricultural development. *Sustainability in Food and Agriculture* **1**(1): 37–41. doi:10.26480/sfna.01.2020.37.41.
- AYUNINGUTAMI, P.I., and NAJICHA, F.U. 2022. Regulasi hukum terhadap penerapan program reforma agraria dalam lingkup kehutanan. *YUDISIA: Jurnal Pemikiran Hukum Dan Hukum Islam* **13**(1): 39. doi:10.21043/yudisia.v13i1.12899.
- BOBERG-FAZLIĆ, N., LAMPE, M., LASHERAS, P., and SHARP, P. 2022. Winners and losers from agrarian reform: evidence from danish land inequality 1682–1895. *Journal of Development Economics*. doi:10.1016/j.jdeveco.2021.102813.
- BUDI, KARTODIHARDJO, H., NUGROHO, B., and MARDIANA, R. 2021. Implementation gap of social forestry policy: the case of HKm Beringin Jaya and HTR Hajran. *Jurnal Manajemen Hutan Tropika* **27**(1): 1–14.
- CARSON, S.L., KENTATCHIME, F., NANA, E.D., NJABO, K.Y., COLE, B.L., and GODWIN, H.A. 2018. Indigenous peoples’ concerns about loss of forest knowledge: implications for forest management. *Conservation and Society* **16**(4): 431–40. doi:10.4103/cs.cs_17_105.
- CATUR, N., WULAN, R.R., WULANDARI, A., NOFHA, R., DEWI, J.K., and AL GHOZALJ, C.M. 2025. Examining communication strategy and implementation of the social forestry program of the Ministry of Environment and Forestry Indonesia in Bandung West Java. *Cogent Social Sciences* **11**(1). doi:10.1080/23311886.2025.2527391.
- CHANDRA, B.R., ROY, A., VINAY, P., KAUR, N., JHA, S., and PRADHAN, N.R. 2025. Forest 5.0: internet of things-based transformation of forests. *Internet Technology Letters* **8**(4). doi:10.1002/itl2.600.
- DITJEN PSKL KLHK. 2015. *Rencana Strategis Direktorat Jenderal Perhutanan Sosial dan Kemitraan Lingkungan Tahun 2015–2019*.
- DITJEN PSKL KLHK. 2017. Publikasi. <http://pskl.menlhk.go.id/publikasi.html>.
- EKOWANTI, M.R.L., TAMRIN, M.H., and MADANIYAH, R.N. 2025. Challenges and policy framework of hazardous and poisonous waste management in Indonesia: policy implementation and public impact. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* **1473**(1): 012064. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1473/1/012064.
- FATEM, S., AWANG, S.A., PUDYATMOKO, S., SAHIDE, M.A.K., PRATAMA, A.A., and MARYUDI, A. 2018. Camouflaging economic development agendas with forest conservation narratives: a strategy of lower governments for gaining authority in the re-centralising Indonesia. *Land Use Policy* **78**: 699–710. doi:10.1016/J.LANDUSEPOL.2018.07.018.
- GARRETT, R.D., CAMMELLI, F., FERREIRA, J., LEVY, S.A., VALENTIM, J., and VIEIRA, I. 2021. Forests and sustainable development in the Brazilian Amazon: history, trends, and future prospects. *Annual Review of Environment and Resources* **46**: 625–52. doi:10.1146/annurev-environ-012220-010228.
- HASTANGKA. 2020. Doktrin filsafat politik Jokowi dan janji Nawacita (mengurai gagasan revolusi mental). *Jurnal Pancasila* **1**(2): 39–44.

- JOPANG, J., TUNDA, A., and TARIFU, L. 2022. BUM desa: strategi pengembangan untuk transformasi sosial ekonomi desa (studi di Kabupaten Konawe Utara, Sulawesi Tenggara). *NeoRespublica: Jurnal Ilmu Pemerintahan*. doi:10.52423/neores.v3i2.25611.
- KLHK, DITJEN PSKL. 2023. Publikasi Ditjen PSKL. <http://pskl.menlhk.go.id/publikasi/publikasi-ditjen-pskl/664-publikasi-tahun-2023.html>.
- LANGSETH, I., JACOBSEN, D.Y., and HAUGSBAKKEN, H. 2023. Correction: the role of support units in digital transformation: how institutional entrepreneurs build capacity for online learning in higher education. *Technology, Knowledge and Learning* **28**(4): 1783–85. doi:10.1007/s10758-022-09622-w.
- LAWASI, M.A. 2024. Unveiling the shortcomings of social forestry programs in Indonesia: a critical analysis of farmer empowerment initiatives. *Jurnal Sylva Lestari* **12**(3): 866–89. doi:10.23960/jsl.v12i3.945.
- MENTERI LHK. 2015. *Rencana Strategis Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup Dan Kehutanan Tahun 2015–2019*.
- MENTERI LHK. 2020. *Rencana Strategis Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup Dan Kehutanan THUN 2020–2024*.
- MEN LHK. 2016. *Peraturan Menteri Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan Nomor P.83/MENLHK/SETJEN/KUM.1/10/2016 Tentang Perhutanan Sosial*. 1–45.
- MEN LHK. 2017. *Peraturan Menteri Lingkungan Hidup Dan Kehutanan Republik Indonesia Nomor 39 Tahun 2017 Tentang Perhutanan Sosial Di Wilayah Kerja Perum Perhutani*. 16.
- MEN LHK. 2021. *Peta Indikatif dan Area Perhutanan Sosial Revisi (Revisi VII)*. 1–10.
- MEN LHK. 2022. Keputusan Menteri Lingkungan Hidup Dan Kehutanan Nomor SK.287/MENLHK/SETJEN/PLA.2/4/2022 Tentang Penetapan Kawasan Hutan Dengan Pengelolaan Khusus pada sebagian hutan negara yang berada pada kawasan hutan produksi dan hutan lindung di Provinsi Jawa Tengah.
- MENLHK. 2023. *Peta Indikatif Dan Areal Perhutanan Sosial (Revisi VIII)*.
- NUGROHO, A.I., BASUNI, S., JUNAEDI, G., KUSUMAH, P.A., HARDJASMITA, K., KUSUMAWINATA, A., DJUWITA, F., RAHMAWATI, K., JUNIANDRI, A., ARDESIANTO, BANGUN, F.B., FADHLI, M., MURPRATIWI, L., and MUNIATI, S. 2021. Strategi on releasing non-productive of forest of onversion area for tora program in Riau Province. *Jurnal Analisis Kebijakan Kehutanan* **18**(1): 1–16. doi:10.20886/jakk.2021.18.1.1-16.
- NURFATRIANI, F., ERWIDODO, TARIGAN, H., and PERKASA, H.W. 2023. The role of the social forestry programs in increasing farmers' income and conserving forests in the Upstream Citarum Watershed, West Java, Indonesia. *International Forestry Review* **25**(2): 211–22. doi:10.1505/146554823837244455.
- PAMBUDI, A.S. 2020. The development of social forestry in Indonesia: policy implementation review, 2007–2019. *The Journal of Indonesia Sustainable Development Planning* **1**(1): 57–66. doi:10.46456/jisdep.v1i1.11.
- PANE, E., YANIS, A.M., and SUSANTO, I. 2021. Social forestry: the balance between welfare and ecological justice. *International Journal of Criminology and Sociology* **10**: 71–78. doi:10.6000/1929-4409.2021.10.10.
- PELUSO, N., and POFFENBERGER, M. 1989. Social forestry in Java: reorienting management systems. *Human Organization* **48**(4): 333–44. doi:10.17730/humo.48.4.a4r82227p5065638.
- PRESIDEN RI. 2015. Perpres Nomor 16 Tahun 2015 Tentang Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup Dan Kehutanan. *Lembaran Negara Republik Indonesia Tahun 2015 Nomor 17* **1**(1).
- PRESIDEN RI. 2020a. *Peraturan Presiden Republik Indonesia No.92 Tahun 2020 Tentang Kementerian Lingkungan Hidup dan Kehutanan*. 2(042491).
- PRESIDEN RI. 2020b. Undang-Undang Republik Indonesia Nomor 11 Tahun 2020 Tentang Cipta Kerja. *Republik Indonesia* 418.
- PRESIDEN RI. 2021. *Peraturan Pemerintah Indonesia Nomor 23 Tahun 2021 Tentang Penyelenggaraan Kehutanan*.
- PUJO, SOFHANI, T.F., GUNAWAN, B., and SYAMSUDIN, T.S. 2018. Community capacity building in social forestry development: a review. *Journal of Regional and City Planning* **29**(2): 113–26. doi:10.5614/jrcp.2018.29.2.3.
- RAHMI, E., FITRIA, F., EKO, NURIYATMAN, T.Y., and TOSCANY, A.N. 2025. Strengthening the coordination function of the forestry ministry: legal reform in the 'Merah Putih' Cabinet for modern bureaucracy. *Journal of Law and Legal Reform* **6**(4): 2177–2218. doi:10.15294/jllr.v6i4.22067.
- RAKATAMA, A., and PANDIT, R. 2020. Reviewing social forestry schemes in Indonesia: opportunities and challenges. *Forest Policy and Economics* **111**(1): 102052. doi:10.1016/j.forpol.2019.102052.
- RAMADHAN, R., and AMALIA, R.N. 2021. Analisis narasi/diskursus terhadap kebijakan perhutanan sosial di wilayah kerja Perhutani. *Wahana Forestra: Jurnal Kehutanan* **16**(1): 1–13.
- ROBLES, W. 2018. Revisiting agrarian reform in Brazil, 1985–2016. *Journal of Developing Societies* **34**(1): 1–34. doi:10.1177/0169796X17749658.
- SAMBODO, B.W., and WAHYUNI. 2015. *Peraturan Direktur Kemitraan Lingkungan Nomor P.01/KL-8/2015 Tentang Rencana Strategis Direktorat Kemitraan Lingkungan Tahun 2015–2019*.
- SANTIKA, T., WILSON, K.A., BUDIHARTA, S., KUSWORO, A., MEIJAARD, E., LAW, E.A., FRIEDMAN, R., HUTABARAT, J.A., INDRAWAN, T.P., JOHN, F.A.V.S., and STRUEBIG, M.J. 2019. Heterogeneous impacts of community forestry on forest conservation and poverty alleviation: evidence from Indonesia edited by J. McPherson. *People and Nature* **1**(2): 204–19. doi:10.1002/pan3.25.
- SUPRIYANTO, B., INTAN, P.J., NURYANTO, I., and HASNAWIR. 2024. Integrated area development: a new social forestry landscape approach in Indonesia. *IOP Conference Series: Earth and Environmental Science* **1299**(1): 012006. doi:10.1088/1755-1315/1299/1/012006.

- SUPRIYANTO, H., SUDARMO, S., and SETYOWATI, K. 2021. Implementation of social forestry in Perum Perhutani KPH Telawa. *Jurnal Analisis Kebijakan Kehutanan* **18**(1): 31–43. doi:10.20886/jakk.2021.18.1.31-43.
- SYANURISMA, S. 2022. Villages in forest areas in Java: agrarian reform policy-social forestry in Banyuwangi. *Marcapada: Jurnal Kebijakan Pertanahan* **1**(2): 123–38. doi:10.31292/mj.v1i2.12.
- WARYANTA. 2016. Reforma agraria: momentum mewujudkan kemandirian ekonomi masyarakat kecil dalam mendukung ketahanan pangan. *Jurnalbhumi.Stpn.Ac.Id* **2**(2): 179.
- WICAKSONO, M.B.A., HANDAYANI, I.G.A.K.R., and KARJOKO, L. 2019. State policy's analysis in the redistribution of reformed agrarian lands from forest areas in Indonesia (Study of Presidential Regulation Number 86 Year 2018 regarding Agrarian Reform). Pp. 174–78 in *Proceedings of the 3rd International Conference on Globalization of Law and Local Wisdom (ICGLOW 2019)*. Vol. **358**. Paris, France: Atlantis Press.
- WIDIYANTO, A., NURROCHMAT, D.R., TRISON, S., SUBARUDI, and NURFATRIANI, F. 2025. Social forestry institutional transformation under the State Forest Area with Special Management (KHDPK) policy. *Asian Journal of Forestry* **9**(2): 196–209. doi:10.13057/asianjfor/r090204.
- WIDODO, J., and KALLA, J. 2014. *Jalan perubahan untuk Indonesia yang berdaulat, mandiri, dan berkepribadian (Joko Widodo-Yusuf Kalla 2014: Visi, Misi, Dan Program Aksi)*. Jakarta.
- FERDIAN, K.J., and ODE, S. 2018. Reforma agraria belum berakhir menuju kesejahteraan masyarakat adat melalui reforma agraria pemerintahan Joko Widodo dan Jusuf Kalla. *Jurnal Sosial Soedirman* **2**(1). doi:10.20884/1.juss.2018.2.1.1182.
- WONG, G.Y., MOELIONO, M., BONG, I.W., PHAM, T.T., SAHIDE, M.A.K., NAITO, D., and BROCKHAUS, M.. 2020. Social forestry in Southeast Asia: evolving interests, discourses and the many notions of equity. *Geoforum* **117**: 246–58. doi:10.1016/j.geoforum.2020.10.010.
- ZAKARIA, R.Y., WIYONO, E.B., FIRDAUS, A.Y., SUHARJITO, D., MUHSI, M.A., SUWITO, SALAM, R., APRIANTO, T.C., and ULİYAH, L. 2018. *Perhutanan sosial: dari slogan menjadi program*. Jakarta: Sekretariat Reforma Agraria dan Perhutanan Sosial.
- ZULKARNAIN, A.A. 2021. Strategi kebijakan percepatan perhutanan sosial di Provinsi Riau. *Journal of Governance Innovation* **3**(2): 172–88. doi:10.36636/jogiv.v3i2.822.